

PHOTOVOLTAIC CHARACTERISTICS OF DYE SENSITIZED SOLAR CELL (DSSC) FABRICATED BY NANO-PARTICLE DEPOSITION SYSTEM (NPDS)

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Several methods for fabricating a dye sensitized solar cell (DSSC) are introduced for enhancing its photo-characteristics [1, 2]. The novel method, nano-particle deposition system (NPDS), suggests one of the outstanding ways to be applied in DSSC. NPDS is a novel method to deposit ceramic and metallic powders on substrate at room temperature, by accelerating particles up to supersonic velocity [3]. NPDS is a modified version of aerosol deposition method (ADM) and cold gas dynamic spray method (CGDS) [4,5]. While ADM uses vacuum condition to accelerate only ceramic powders to deposit on the substrate, CGDS requires high pressure of carrier gas for metallic powder deposition. It is hard to deposit metallic powders using ADM with low particle velocity, however, using CGDS, the 10~100 μm of metallic powders can be deposited on the substrates [6]. To overcome these limitations of two methods, NPDS allows deposition of various

types of powders simultaneously. It uses relatively low carrier gas pressure and low vacuum chamber. Moreover, the processing temperature is relatively low compared to other deposition process such as chemical vapor deposition so that it can be applied on a flexible substrate.

In this study, NPDS is used to fabricate TiO₂ layer which is a working electrode for DSSC. Using this method, dry and nano-sized TiO₂ powders were sprayed on the Indium tin oxide (ITO) glass instead of paste type of TiO₂.

Conventionally, TiO₂ paste for working electrode has been fabricated using paste type method. The paste composed of mixture of nano-sized TiO₂ powders, binders and solutions, is then painted on ITO glass. After drying, TiO₂ layer on TCO glass is sintered to make a path for electron transfer. TiO₂ layers formed by this paste type method, however, require numerous steps which can be time consuming. In this study, TiO₂ powders were directly sprayed on ITO glass using NPDS in order to simplify its fabrication steps. To obtain its desirable deposition thickness and adhesion for absorbing enough dye, sonication was performed for its proper surface condition. Finally, several steps of deposition processes were repeated to obtain TiO₂ layer with its thickness more than 20 μm . To assemble DSSC, sealing sheet was used to bond two electrodes to prevent volatilization of liquid electrolyte. Different thicknesses of sealing sheets were used to bond two electrodes. Since the thickness of the deposited TiO₂ layer is less than 20 μm , the thickness of sealing sheets which is thicker than 25 μm , can be the gap between two electrodes. Since the amount of electrolyte can

Fig1. Schematic diagram of NPDS [3].

directly be affected by the gap which controls electron transferring rate and recombination rate of E-H, the thickness of sealing sheets is a remarkably important factor to determine the photo-characteristics of cell.

Moreover, commercial TiO₂ powders with different sizes were alternately deposited to make proper morphologies to give high photovoltaic efficiencies [7]. Powders with different sizes are mixed and they were deposited on ITO glass for increasing its light absorption rate. Microstructure of TiO₂ layers was observed by Scanning Electronic Microscope (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM). The photo-characteristic was measured by the solar simulator and Incident-Photon-to-electron Conversion Efficiency (IPCE) for comparison. The result of cell efficiency of DSSC with TiO₂ layers deposited by NPDS indicates that NPDS is a promising method to fabricate TiO₂ layer for DSSC.

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